
Recreational Facilities as a Universal Remedy towards Worthy Physical Shape and Longevity: Case Study of Igbomina Kingdom.

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Abstract

The main objective is to examine the availability of recreational facilities, recreational activities and facilities usage and impact on the people of Igbomina land. Data were collected from the five (5) local government areas in both Osun and Kwara states that made up of Igbomina land in Nigeria, Seven hundred (700) questionnaires were used. Based on the respondents' demographic data and opinions regarding the availability and use of recreational facilities in their domains, the results and discussions of the results were presented. Convenience sampling technique was employed in data collection of people under study. The data was computed and analyzed using SPSS; the Mean and Standard Deviation were used for analysis. The 2.50 mean standard was employed to consider a certain opinion to be important. According to the report, the main pastimes and recreations that individuals partake in are sports, cooking, going to restaurants, going to church, and walking and running. The respondents concurred that engaging in leisure and recreational activities lengthens their life expectancy and enhances their physical well-being and quality of life. The public should view leisure and recreation as a vital tool for improving well-being, reducing stress, and raising standards of living. We also advise everyone, including those residing on Igbomina land, to engage in leisure activities on a daily basis. The study recommends that the Federal, State, and local government agencies (LGA) should provide recreational centers and make necessary facilities available in key locations within each LGA. Adequate orientations should be provided through the National Orientation Agency (NOA).

Keywords: Longevity, Sport Facilities, Recreation, Wellbeing, Satisfaction.

Introduction

According to Dong (2014), researches have studied leisure/recreation using the following approaches: outdoor recreation (Ferris, 1962), time use (Szalai, 1972), psychological perspectives (Ragheb, 1980), social context (Kelly, 1983), consumer behaviors (Mitchell, 1983), seriousness (Stebbins, 1992), lifestyles (Simpson & Cheney, (2007; Dong & Chick, 2012). The advocates of Outdoor Recreation Resources Review Commission, (ORRRC) categorized recreation constraints into three types, Interpersonal, Intrapersonal and Structural Constraints.

It is believed that psychological elements like stress, depression, or mood are examples of intrapersonal constraints. Interpersonal limitations include things like neighbors, coworkers, friends, and family. Factors like time constraints, hectic schedules, and activity expenses are examples of structural constraints. Chick and Dong (2005) on their own point of view stated that cultural constraints should be included.

For this study we are going to look at these other factors that are not extensively included in the previous researches, the factors to be included are, age, gender, religion, profession and education.

During the past two or three decade cases of depression, hypertension, and stroke have been so alarming. Suicide is not also left unnoticed in communities. Many researchers have been on how to cure the emergency of this ugly situation through drugs. This study intends to proffer preventive measures. Preventive measures will go a long way to eradicate the challenges and thereby demand for medicine may be drastically reduced.

(Wilmore), (1994), Ajala et Bolarinwa ,(2002) and Adeogun, (2004), agree to the fact that stress is a change in what body is used to, it refers to as disturbance in the body's homeostatic, which results in changes in equilibrium and requires adapting to the physical and social environment. Stress could be a factor that lead to many of the health challenges in communities. Human body system (heart, blood vessels, the immune system, the lungs, the brains and the sensory organs of the body) respond to stress differently in this manner, it constitutes the gravity of likely health challenges. Among the several ways to manage stress, using some physical activities could serve in reducing stress. So also practise some type of mind relaxation activities. Recreations are of different types. Everyone determines his/her preferred choice and engages in doing it regularly and correctly.

Regular recreation either in isolation or amidst colleagues could regulate to a large extent body's reaction to stress. With recreation depression and boredom is addressed and sent packing. Adequate recreational education and facilities will boost the morale of those people and assist them in managing their stresses.

Constant and effective making use of recreations could be a very important factor in maintaining good health. It should be a thing of concern for some philanthropists to look inward towards provision of recreational amenities in communities to put an end to regular occurrence of cases of depression, stress, stroke and suicide.

Methodology

The study utilized a multi-phase sampling approach. Initially, data regarding the prevalence of selected illnesses will be obtained from local healthcare facilities. The purpose is to

ascertain the level of damages the lack of recreational education information has done to the community.

Another area is the administering of questionnaires. Questionnaires were given to indigents who were purposively selected in the area of jurisdiction of this study. The information collected include personal information such as gender, age, profession, religion, marital status, educational level, household size, previous place of abode and health history of each of the participants.

Before we presented the questionnaires, the participants were asked for their consent in a letter addressed to the LGA authorities. They were promised that their personal data would remain secure, and all data obtained was processed with the absolute secrecy.

Data Analysis and Interpretation of Results

This session includes a case study of Igbomina Kingdom and the outcomes of data analysis, interpretation, and debate on recreational facilities as a universal treatment towards worthy physical shape and lifespan.

Table 1 : Gender of the Respondents

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>Male</i>	356	50.9
<i>Female</i>	344	49.1
<i>Total</i>	700	100.0

As can be seen from the above table, a very balanced range of participants were contacted, suggesting that the investigators sought for data from a diverse range of respondents to validate the quality of the data collected.. As shown in the table above, 356 (50.9%) respondents are male, and female are 344 (49.1%).

Table 2 : Age distribution of the Respondents

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>18-26</i>	96	13.7
<i>27-35</i>	102	14.6
<i>36-44</i>	104	14.9
<i>45-54</i>	159	22.7
<i>55-64</i>	109	15.6
<i>65-69</i>	52	7.4
<i>70 and above</i>	78	11.1
<i>Total</i>	700	100.0

From Table 2 above, 96 (13.7%) respondents are between 18-26 years old, 102 (14.6%) are between the ages of 27 and 35, and 104 (14.9%) are between the ages of 36 and 44., 159 (22.7%) respondents are between 45-54 years old, 109 (15.4%) are of the ages 55-64 years old, 52 (7.4%) while only 78 (11,1%) are of age 70 and above.

Table 3: State / Local government of Origin Of he Respondents

<i>State / Lga</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Osun: <i>Ila</i>	215	30.7
<i>Ifedayo</i>	157	22.4
Kwara: <i>Irepodun</i>	109	15.6
<i>Ifelodun</i>	114	16.3
<i>Isin</i>	105	15.0
Total	700	100.0

From table 3, it will be observed that, Ila local government area has the highest number of the respondents of 215 (30.7%), Ifedayo with 157 (22.4%), Irepodun in Kwara state with 109 (15.6%) respondents also Ifelodun has 114 (16.3%) of the respondents while Isin have the lowest number of 105(15.0%) of respondents. This shows a wide distribution of questionnaires to the concerned local government areas of interest. Ila local government has the highest number of respondents being the headquarters of Igbomina land and also have the highest populaion in terms of human resources and landscape in Igbomina land.

Table 4: Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Single</i>	51	7.3
<i>Married</i>	404	57.7
<i>Widow / Widower</i>	150	21.4
<i>Divorced</i>	95	13.6
Total	700	100.0

Table 4 above shows that the majority of the respondents are married, with 404 (57.7%), while only 51(7.3) are singles, 150 (21.2%) are either widow or widower, also, 95 (13.6%) of the respondents are divorced.

Table 5 : Religion of the Respondents

Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Christianity</i>	327	46.7
<i>Islam</i>	341	48.7
<i>Traditional</i>	32	4.6
Total	700	100.0

Table 5 above shows the religions of the respondents with 341 (48.7%) being muslims, while 327 (46.7%) are christians and only 32 (4.6%) are traditional worshipers.

Table 6: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Highest Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>SSCE/WAEC</i>	76	10.9
<i>NCE/ND</i>	106	15.1
<i>HND/BSC</i>	254	36.3
<i>MASTER</i>	163	23.3
<i>PhD</i>	101	14.4
Total	700	100.0

Above table 6 indicates that 101 (14.4%) respondents have PhD, 163 (23.3%) have master degrees, 254 (36.3%) bagged either HND or BSc while 106 (15.1%) respondents had NCE or ND certificates and only 76 (10.9%) of the respondents had either SSCE or WAEC certificates.

Table 7: Occupation of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Artisans</i>	96	13.7
<i>Farmers</i>	42	6.0
<i>Government Workers</i>	321	45.9
<i>Traders</i>	123	17.6
<i>Students</i>	104	14.9
<i>Others</i>	14	2.0
Total	700	100.0

From Table 7 above, It is noted that most of the participants, 321 (45.9%) are government workers with either the local, state or federal government. 96 (13.7%) are artisans, 42 (6.0%) are farmers, 123 (17.6%) are traders of one goods or the other, while 104 (14.9%) are students of higher institutions and only 14 (2.0%) are for other occupations.

Table 8: Size of the Household of the Respondents

Family Size	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>1-2</i>	89	12.7
<i>3-4</i>	341	48.7
<i>5-6</i>	221	31.6
<i>7 and above</i>	49	7.0
Total	700	100.0

Table 8 above indicates that 89 (12.7%) respondents have a family size of between 1 and 2, 341 (48.7%) have between 3 and 4, then 221 (31.6%) household have 5 to 6 members while, only 49 (7.0%) have seven and above members of their households.

Table 9: Health Status of the Respondents

Health Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Poor</i>	221	31.6
<i>Fair</i>	317	45.3
<i>Good</i>	92	13.1
<i>Excellent</i>	70	10.0
Total	700	100.0

Table 9 is all about the health status of the respondents, we can deduce from above that most of the respondents have one ailment or the other they are nursing, 221 (31.6%) have poor health, 317 (45.3%) have fair health status, 92 (13.1%) have good health, while only 70 (10.0%) can boast of excellent health status.

Table 10: Availability of Recreational Facilities in the LGAs

Recreational Facilities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Available</i>	64	9.1
<i>Not Available</i>	589	84.1
<i>Do not Know</i>	47	6.8
Total	700	100.0

Table 11: Performing Recreational activities at Leisure Time

Recreational Activities at Leisure Time	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Daily</i>	75	10.7
<i>weekly</i>	177	25.3
<i>monthly</i>	22	3.1
<i>Once in a while</i>	426	60.9
Total	700	100.0

According to Table 10, the majority of respondents, 589 (84.1%), stated that there are no recreational facilities in their domains; 64 (9.1%) stated that there are; and 47 (6.8%) stated they are unsure about the availability of the facilities.

As indicated in table 11, 75 (10.7%) respondents performs one recreational activity or the other daily, 177 (25.3%) recreate weekly while only 22 respondents engages in one or more recreation activities monthly and 426 (60.9%) only engage in recreational activities once in a while.

Table 12: Role of Leisure/Recreation in Improving Psychological Wellness

S/N	Items/Factors	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Leisure activities gives me a sense of belonging/satisfaction	2.83	0.41	Accept
2	Leisure/recreational activities help me in relieving stress	2.76	0.34	Accept
3	Leisure activities e.g. swimming help me to reduce depression	2.66	0.37	Accept
4	Recreational activities help me to conquer boredom	3.38	0.44	Accept
5	Leisure activities help to increase my patience	3.32	0.29	Accept
6	Leisure activities help me keep my emotions under control	3.17	0.46	Accept
7	Recreation helps me to explore my inner spirit and sense of creativity	2.96	0.32	Accept
8	Engaging in recreational activity helps me to eliminate loneliness	3.22	0.27	Accept
9	Leisure activities help to reduce my tension	3.74	0.22	Accept
10	Recreation makes me to be more lively	2.90	0.45	Accept
11	Leisure/recreational activities provide me the chance to find balance in my life	3.22	0.35	Accept
12	Leisure and recreation creates in me, clarity of mind	2.67	0.34	Accept
13	Participating in leisure/recreation is capable of improving my longevity	2.74	0.33	Accept
Pooled Mean		3.04		Accept
Benchmark Mean		2.50		

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

High productivity, positive interpersonal relationships at work, in the family, and in society, as well as creativity and social flexibility, are all positively correlated with psychological well-being (Rajgopal, 2010; Trotter, 2008). The results of Kwom, Pickett, Lee, and Lee (2018), who also discovered a positive correlation between leisure activities and psychological wellness and the fact that individuals who regularly participate in leisure activities tend to be more psychologically stable and sound than those who do not, corroborate this finding.

Table 13: Role of Leisure/Recreation in Improving Physical Wellness

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Leisure activities reduce my anxiousness	3.22	0.23	Accept
2	Leisure activities had contributed immensely in promoting my physical health	3.65	0.46	Accept
3	Leisure/recreation reduces my risk of contacting diseases	2.66	0.45	Accept
4	I look and feel smart after engaging in leisure/recreational activity	3.47	0.35	Accept
5	Leisure/recreational activities improves the quality of my life	2.87	0.26	Accept
6	Leisure and recreation lowers my blood pressure	2.77	0.30	Accept
7	Leisure/recreational activities promote my health and wellbeing	3.71	0.41	Accept
8	Leisure/Recreation increases my fitness	3.55	0.66	Accept
9	Recreational activities improve my physical and mental health	3.67	0.39	Accept
10	Leisure/recreational activities help to prevent me from developing chronic diseases such as Osteoporosis	2.73	0.47	Accept
11	Recreational activities help me to maintain my body weight and lower body mass index	3.05	0.32	Accept
12	Leisure activities help to increase my muscle strength, joint	3.59	0.45	Accept

	flexibility and lower total cholesterol levels			
13	Leisure and recreation helps to reduce my chances of heart problems	2.81	0.53	Accept
14	Leisure/recreation helps to boost my immune system	3.12	0.27	Accept
Pooled Mean		3.21		Accept
Benchmark Mean		2.50		

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The Findings on the Role of Leisure in Improving Physical Wellness found that leisure activities improve quality of life, improve physical health, reduce the risk of developing diseases, make you look fit and healthy, strengthen the immune system, improve fitness, improve mental health and maintain body weight, lower BMI and BP, increase muscle strength, reduce heart related problems and increase life expectancy (Longevity). This is true because most leisure activities involve engaging in one or more light physical activities and research has shown that light physical activities, such as walking or even exercising your brain with simple tasks or brain exercises that take your mind off of everyday stressors, can have a significant effect on your physical health. According to the study, all 14 elements/factors that evaluated the impact of leisure / recreation on the well-being of the inhabitants of Igbomina land met the 2.50 standard and were all considered as significant. Therefore, the respondents agreed that leisure / recreation improves patience, decreases tension, keeps emotions in check, lowers depression, reduces stress, builds self-confidence, increases creativity, eliminates loneliness, helps create balance in one's life, improves clarity of mind and longevity, and increases appreciation of one's immediate surroundings. The pooled mean average value of 3.21 further supports the assumption that all of the items in Table 12 were acknowledged by the respondents as to how leisure and recreation enhance mental wellness, as indicated by the mean responses for all of the items being above the 2.50 cut-off. Daily stress can significantly affect one's physical health.

The study found that recreational activities can improve psychological wellness in the following ways: they can help people learn to value their surroundings, explore their creative side, live longer, manage their emotions, relieve tension, increase patience, lessen depression, and relieve stress. They can also help people develop a positive self-esteem.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, there are many benefits to derive by engaging in leisure and recreational activities. Leisure and recreational activities may play an educational role; it can influence international and community development, promote health, and socio cultural which also stimulate economy. Leisure and recreation influences physical well-being, It enriches the Quality of Life as a whole. High Quality of Life index represents desired satisfaction of people living in a geographical area, so leisure and recreation can become a tool for achieving all these. Therefore, people in this communities should see leisure and recreation as important and vital tool in improving good physical shape and wellbeing, as it plays important role in boosting the quality of life cutting across physical and emotional vitality. The people should engage in leisure and recreational activities to lengthens their life expectancy and enhances their physical well-being and quality of life. The public should view leisure and recreation as a vital tool for improving well-being, reducing stress, and raising standards of living. It is also advise that everyone, including those residing on Igbomina land, to engage in leisure activities on a daily basis. Also, Federal, State, and local government agencies (LGA) should provide recreational centers and make necessary facilities available in key locations within

each LGA. Adequate orientations should be provided through the National Orientation Agency (NOA).

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